

D7.3

Dissemination strategy and activities

Project number:	871518
Project acronym:	COLLABS
Project title:	A COmprehensive cyber-intelligence framework for resilient coLLABorative manufacturing Systems
Start date of the project:	1 st January, 2020
Duration:	36 months
Programme:	ICT-08-2019

Deliverable type:	Report
Deliverable reference number:	DS-01-871518/ D7.3 /2.0
Work package contributing to the deliverable:	WP7
Due date:	12 2020 - M12
Actual submission date:	28 th December 2020

Responsible organisation:	UNIPD
Editor:	Gulshan Kumar
Dissemination level:	PU
Revision:	2.0

<i>Abstract:</i>	<i>This deliverable lists the main dissemination actions performed within the 1st year of the project as well as lists the strategical plan for proceeding years to disseminate various findings and events organized by the COLLABS partners.</i>
<i>Keywords:</i>	<i>Dissemination, Events, Workshop, Social Media</i>

The project COLLABS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 871518.

Editor

Gulshan Kumar and Muhammad Hassan, UniPD

Contributors

All partners

Version	Date	By	Overview
<i>2.0</i>	<i>24/12/2020</i>	<i>Gulshan Kumar</i>	<i>Revisions Incorporated, Paper ready for submission</i>
<i>1.2</i>	<i>22/12/2020</i>	<i>Ernesto Gomez Marin</i>	<i>Reviewed version</i>
<i>1.1</i>	<i>22/12/2020</i>	<i>Alzahraa Alhaddad</i>	<i>Reviewed version</i>
<i>1.0</i>	<i>20/12/2020</i>	<i>Gulshan Kumar</i>	<i>1st Full version</i>
<i>0.2</i>	<i>25/09/2020</i>	<i>Muhammad Hassan</i>	<i>1st Draft</i>
<i>0.1</i>	<i>09/09/2020</i>	<i>Muhammad Hassan</i>	<i>First Draft - ToC</i>

Disclaimer

The information in this document is provided “as is”, and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The content of this document reflects only the author`s view - the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. The users use the information at their sole risk and liability.

Executive Summary

The main goal of dissemination and communication is to raise awareness of the project activities, in order to make COLLABS a successful and sustainable project. This will be carried out by using various communication channels and materials, such as press releases, website updates, along with face-to-face interactions which includes seminars or invited talks, conferences and workshops.

During dissemination, the major task will be to make use of the European Commission communication best practices to define dissemination plans and to select appropriate tools to be used by the consortium for both internal and external communication. The main elements of dissemination plan will be the tasks, responsible partners, materials used, audience addressed and timing.

The key objectives of the dissemination strategy are:

- *To make known as widely as possible the findings and recommendations of the COLLABS to engage with and elicit feedback from stakeholders on the project's deliverables.*
- *To stimulate discussion among stakeholders of the project's findings and recommendations.*
- *To facilitate and enable close collaboration between different categories of stakeholders and relevant IIoT programmers, cyber security consultants.*
- *To strengthen the research and knowledge base of both researchers and end-users.*

In this document, we have aggregated the individual strategies of the COLLABS collaborators to obtain a pathway about the dissemination and communication work. This will also help to negotiate the future plans and also getting a glimpse of future thoughts about the project.

Contents

List of Tables	8
List of Abbreviations	9
Introduction	10
<i>Purpose and scope</i>	10
Communication and Dissemination	10
<i>Dissemination plan and communication activities objectives</i>	10
<i>Guiding principles of the Communication and Marketing Strategy</i>	11
<i>Responsibilities</i>	11
<i>Dissemination and communication levels</i>	11
<i>Target Audience</i>	11
<i>Communication messages</i>	12
<i>Logo and graphical identity</i>	12
<i>Templates</i>	13
<i>Channels of dissemination</i>	13
<i>Identification of stakeholders</i>	13
Dissemination and Communication tools	16
<i>Project flyer</i>	17
<i>Project brochure</i>	17
<i>Project website and database</i>	17
<i>Press releases and articles</i>	18
<i>Social media, including Twitter & blogs</i>	18
Events	19
<i>Organization and Presentation in Workshops, Seminars & Conferences</i>	19
<i>International events</i>	20

<i>Initial international workshops</i>	20
<i>Advanced international workshops</i>	20
<i>International Conferences</i>	20
<i>Local workshops</i>	21
Dissemination and Communication Events by Each Partner	23
<i>Dissemination and communication plan by each partner</i>	23
<i>Commissariat A L Energie Atomique Et Aux Energies Alternatives (CEA)</i>	23
<i>Foundation for Research & Technology Hellas (FORTH)</i>	24
<i>PHILIPS Consumer Lifestyle B.V. (PCL)</i>	24
<i>Infineon Technologies AG (IFAG)</i>	26
<i>Advanced Laboratory on Embedded Systems SRL (UTRC)</i>	26
<i>University of Novi Sad Faculty of Sciences (UNSPMF)</i>	27
<i>Sphynx Technology Solutions AG (STS)</i>	28
<i>Thales SIX GTS FR SAS (TSG)</i>	29
<i>Information Technology for Market Leadership IKE (ITML)</i>	30
<i>University of Padova (UNIPD)</i>	31
<i>Siemens AG (SAG)</i>	31
<i>Renault SAS (REN)</i>	32
<i>Harokopio University of Athens (HUA)</i>	34
Dissemination and Communication Plan	34
Conclusion	34

List of Tables

Table 1: Mapping of dissemination tools to stakeholder groups..... 21

Table 2: Timetable of communication strategies..... 23

List of Abbreviations

EC	<i>European Commission</i>
WP	<i>Work Package</i>
IOT	<i>Internet of Things</i>
IIOT	<i>Industrial Internet of Things</i>
SWOT	<i>Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats</i>
PEST	<i>Political, Economic, Social, Technological</i>
OT	<i>Operational Technology</i>
SME	<i>Small Medium Enterprise</i>
EEN	<i>Enterprise Europe Network</i>
EU	<i>European Union</i>

Introduction

Purpose and Scope

This document describes the Dissemination Plan and Communication Activities to be adopted by COLLABS - a project funded by European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 871578: A COmprehensive cyber-intelligence framework for resilient collaborative manufacturing Systems. Its purpose is to formalize all communication and dissemination actions planned in the framework of the project, to provide guidelines on the approach and to set out the timeline related to planned events and actions, to ensure that information is shared with appropriate audiences on a timely basis and by the most effective means and channels.

The purpose of the document is:

- *To keep a record of all communication and dissemination plans carried out in the framework of the project.*
- *To proactively promote project results through web and social media, publications (conferences and journals), organization of workshops, summer schools, etc.*
- *To contribute to IIoT activities/events and to monitor/contribute to standardization process.*
- *To provide guidelines on the approach and to set out the key dates related to planned events and actions.*
- *To ensure that information is shared with appropriate audiences on a timely basis and by the most effective means.*

More specifically, the objectives of the dissemination and communication plan are

- *To establish and maintain mechanisms for effective and timely communication of project activities.*
- *To inform stakeholders of the progress of the development and encourage interactions between stakeholders. The dissemination strategy will enable stakeholders to provide feedback on the project's deliverables, which will feed into the project at its various stages.*
- *To coordinate all levels and types of communication in relation to the project.*

This document is intended to be a live folder, which will continuously be enriched with the forthcoming project's achievements and contributions from project partners. In the course of the project, COLLABS partners will continuously review this plan and, finally, a consolidated and updated version will be uploaded on the project website. However, it is expected that the most significant dissemination effort will occur at the beginning of the project to establish the visual identity and during the final year when the principal results will have been achieved.

Communication and dissemination strategy

Dissemination plan and communication activities objectives

The major objectives of COLLABS regarding communication and dissemination are as follows:

- To communicate and disseminate the knowledge produced by the project and all relevant knowledge available at EU level;
- To create a communication platform at EU level for SMEs and EEN members;
- To exploit the results of the project after its lifetime.

Guiding principles of the Communication and Marketing Strategy

The basic motivating principles defined for communication and marketing are as follows:

- Communication processes must be clear and known to all consortium partners;
- Communication and dissemination must be purposeful and timely;
- Dissemination and communication must be open, honest and frank;
- In general, relevant information will be available on an open basis;
- Communication is a two-way process. It is not just a matter of messages being passed down from the coordinator to partners; upward and horizontal communications are equally important.

Responsibilities

University of Padova (UNIPD), Italy, and ALL partners will contribute to information dissemination through conference participation and by organizing talks in different universities around Europe. In addition, the possibility of organizing workshops on the topic will be investigated, as was done for SecureComm 2012 and Sacmat 2013. UNIPD will also present results to “Researchers Night”, as done in 2013 edition, where the research group presented MITHYS work, a system for the mitigation of SSL issues on Android devices.

Each project partner will receive a website manual in order to easily upload press-releases on local events and information about local media publications related to the project, Communication Section. ITML (web administrator) will coordinate that process.

Dissemination and communication levels

The dissemination plan is divided into three strategic focus areas, so that the focus is based on where and when the effort of the dissemination is most needed and effective.

The strategic focus areas are:

- Dissemination at a local level.
- Dissemination at a National level.
- Dissemination at a European level.
- Dissemination at outside the European scope.

Target Audience

The Dissemination and Communication Plan contemplates activities and actions are dedicated to gain the attraction of the following big categories of target groups:

- Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs).
- Trade and Professional associations.
- Enterprise Europe Network members.
- Public authorities.

During the project progress the following key messages will be conveyed to the target audiences:

- Presentation of the project and its overall objectives.
- Presentation of achieved results.
- Dissemination of deliverables and results.

In addition to identifying the target groups/audience to outreach, the major goals are:

- For each group, to consider main concerns and interest that should be communicated.
- For each group, to consider the communication means that would be most effective to pass the messages.

Communication messages

The consortium shall define the message or messages to be transmitted to the several target groups. An evident objective is to focus on positive achievements and the benefits they could bring. This requires clear agreement and careful coordination among all parties who may act as spokespersons or information sources for a particular project or network. Inconsistent facts, figures, emphases and viewpoints are to be avoided at all costs.

Key messages to be transmitted:

- What the is project about.
- Aim of the project.
- Potential impact of the project.
- Entities is involved in the project.
- Defining the project's conferences, workshops and events.
- Major developments.
- New organizations and stakeholders involved in the COLLABS network.
- Key milestones of the project.

Logo and graphical identity

A graphical identity is composed of visual elements that aim to represent an organization. The COLLABS graphical identity will include a logo, fonts, colors and text.

It is important to follow the graphical identity, since good use of it will help to consistently communicate and disseminate the project outcomes. Guidelines and templates will also save time and effort for the members of the consortium, since no further design work will be necessary.

A model of the COLLABS logo has been proposed by the lead applicant and finally supported by all project *partners*.

Figure 1: COLLABS logo

Templates

Templates for text documents and Power Point presentations have to be prepared and made accessible for all members of the project. These will be accessible at project's data repository.

The templates are important to give a uniform image of the project and to establish a visual language that will indicate, at a glance, that the presented information concerns the COLLABS project.

Channels of dissemination

In order to reach out the above audiences, COLLABS will use a number of channels and will cooperate with other relevant national and international organizations, programmers and projects sharing similar objectives. The whole consortium could take part in identifying these potentially useful collaborations. In order to achieve this, we propose a collaboration strategy with other projects, organizations, programmers, etc. using the following steps:

- First, identify other EU projects and organizations that would be interested in potential collaboration i.e. where communication/cooperation would be beneficial for all.
- Specify for each identified project or organization areas of interest for cooperation (the purpose is to exchange the know-how, tools, and reuse the existing knowledge).
- Propose a list of actions to be done during the project to enable this cooperation and specify project partners responsible to further explore and support these cooperation possibilities.

Identification of stakeholders

Synthetic collaboration matrix - partner's vs identified projects/organizations for collaboration will be made as a result, based on the outcomes of abovementioned steps. An understanding of stakeholders' interests, drivers and barriers is essential for effective communication and the prioritization of tools for communication. Understanding stakeholder motivations will enable the consortium to effectively engage, communicate with, and promote current and future dialogue between different stakeholders.

Stakeholder engagement is key to the success of any initiative. One of the principal tasks of COLLABS is to identify and characterize stakeholders relevant to the project for the purposes

of: 1) identifying individuals to invite and involve in the projects workshops and 2) disseminating publicity material and key project outputs (e.g., press releases, newsletters, handbook etc.). The identified categories of stakeholders may be updated and redefined as the project progresses.

The different categories of stakeholders identified below have different interests and play different roles towards provisioning IIOT for mass-market domain across application sectors. As such, we must try to understand the different roles that stakeholders play within the different phases of linking and expanding existing eco-systems of smart objects. To realize such vision and with the support and research experience of academic partners (UNPID, HUA, UNSPMF), COLLABS consortium will involve industries from different and heterogeneous domains (PCL, IFAG, STS, REN, UTRC) including object suppliers, consumers and incentives providers, as well as telecom and software provider and technology developers. Such an understanding will help the consortium to optimize its interactions with stakeholders during the course of the project.

The following are the COLLABS key stakeholder categories and their roles:

- IoT-driven industry stakeholders:
 - (i) Utilization of project's results in everyday operations.
 - (ii) Strengthened innovation by blending with in-house artifacts.
 - (iii) Training of project outcomes.
 - (iv) Participation in the project's events.
 - (v) Exploitation of the project's open-source results.
 - (vi) Inspiration for new ideas and applications.
- Researchers and Academia, i.e., individuals engaged in research initiatives and/or working in research/academic institutes conducting core or application research on cyber security, IIoT, data analytics and cloud engineering:
 - (i) Further advancements on the cyber security, IIoT and Data analytics research through extension/reuse of the project's outputs in the investigated and in other application domains.
 - (ii) Inspiration for future research initiatives based on the project's concept and results.
 - (iii) Participation in the project's events.

This category of stakeholders includes various big entities such as Universities, research institutes, think tanks, discipline specific networks and several sub-entities such as research groups, lecturers/ researchers/course developers and PhD students. UNIPD and other higher education institutions, as well as research-oriented institutions will contribute to information dissemination through conference participation and by organizing talks in different universities around Europe. In order to reach out to the interested candidates, these partners will also disseminate the project results through the publications of relevant papers in highly esteemed conferences and journals.

Why we want to reach them?

- To inform them about current and emerging trends relating to create flexible and adaptable smart tags applicable in multiple application sectors in Europe.

-
- To encourage the use of our guidelines, research findings and good practices in respect of Internet of Things.
 - To encourage academics to provide their views with regard to the consortium's findings and recommendations as they are being developed as well as once they have been formulated.
 - To encourage academic organizations and researchers to conduct further research in regard to the issues of concern to the project's themes.
 - To encourage the public to lobby political leaders in support of the consortium's recommendations.
 - To raise their awareness of the challenges faced with regards to their use of technology and the consequent dangers of some technologies and applications.

Whom to reach?

- Industry Associations & Technology Clusters, e.g., European initiatives and clusters, various EU and national unions and major industry associations.
 - i) Inclusion of project's results to collaborative research activities (roadmap, white papers, position papers).
 - ii) Dissemination of project's results to their members.
 - iii) Bilateral participation in events for knowledge exchange.
- Participants, project partners and relevant stakeholders active in the H2020 related to cyber security and IoT industry for the following dimensions:
 - (i) Identification of common topics.
 - (ii) Synergies and collaborations for results promotion.
 - (iii) Enhancing innovation through results combination.
 - (iv) Co-organization of events.
 - (v) Research Agenda formulation.
- Policy makers (at any level like EC Directorates, Ministries and Governments, Regulatory Agencies), Standardization Organizations (ETSI, etc):
 - (i) Evaluation of the project's Social-Technological-Economic-Environmental-Political (STEEP) aspects.
 - (ii) Definition of future research and innovation directions for the EC initiatives, considering the project's acquired knowledge and experience.
 - (iii) Inputs for standardization activities.
- General public (citizens), i.e., individuals who benefit from the project outcomes.
 - (i) Acquire new experience and utilize the project results in scenarios that are addressed to the general public for gathering feedback.
 - (ii) Increase awareness about the broader social and economic benefits of cyber security technologies in industrial settings.

Particular attention is given to the promotion of project outcomes to the general public as an important stakeholder in the COLLABS concept. This will also be achieved using social networks as well as relying on the strengths of marketing and promotion channels of companies.

Dissemination and Communication tools

The communication and discussions activities within the project's Consortium are done using the following methods:

- Face to face meeting (Virtual meetings due to COVID situation).
- Project file repository.
- Regular online conferences (using Skype for Business).
- Mailing lists (One technical e-mail list and one administrative list is used).

The following subtasks will be executed to support the activities identified in the communication and dissemination plan:

- Project presentation, fact sheet and logo will be created to help promoting the main ideas of the project and to create a unique visual identity (M3). During the first year of the project, a short animation will be created to explain the benefits and the potential of COLLABS project. The project's work plan includes various dissemination activities. One of the important tasks through project presentations is identifying individual stakeholders, creating a taxonomy of stakeholders and analyzing their motivations (i.e. their interests, needs and drivers). This task will form the basis of engaging stakeholders through interviews, focus groups, workshops and other means throughout the project and will ensure that the consortium's analyses, findings and recommendations are based on stakeholder reality.
- Website will be created in M3 and then continuously updated throughout the project. The website will contain all information about the project structure, consortium, outputs, progress as well as tools for interaction with potential stakeholders.
- The website will be publicized at project-based and related events by the consortium partners. The individual partners will also publicize the website to their own networks of contacts. The COLLABS website is designed to be informative yet uncomplicated with clear language to ensure wide communication with diverse categories of stakeholders and external audience. Outcome measure: website hits, page views, deliverable/document downloads, comments received, requests for information received.
- Social networks profiles will be created and managed actively throughout the project. Due to the variety of potential users (businesses, consumers) different types of social networks will be used, e.g., LinkedIn for addressing the businesses and Facebook for addressing consumers. Twitter will be also used to provide regular updates about the project activities.
- Public events like workshops and meet-ups will be organized to engage stakeholders in an interactive manner with the goal to capture their feedback and involve them in project pilots and eventually creating a sustainable technological ecosystem.
- UniPD and ALL partners, may plan to disseminate the project results through publications of relevant papers in high quality conferences and journals wherever required. In addition, related content may also be included in tutorials to be presented in major international conferences, workshops, summer schools and other events. Due

to its previous involvement, UniPD will explore the possibility to host tutorial at summer school held at University of Padova.

- Other dissemination and promotional materials like articles for magazines, press releases, appearances at radio and TV, various leaflets, T-shirts etc. will be prepared according to the plan identified in T7.2. Localized versions for each of the participating countries will be made. The Flyers created for promotion of project includes key information such as what is project about, members of consortium, explaining concepts and architecture. These flyers will be created at the start of the project and included on the website for download, distributed manually in project events such as workshops, seminars and conferences. Furthermore, Poster/rollup will also be used to promote the project and later to promote the platform/results to potential users.

Project flyer

- A flyer with an introduction to the project and contact information will be produced within the first year of the project. It will be produced by ITML and supported by the Coordinator. It will be translated in all of the partners languages. The pamphlet will be handed out at all project events and will be uploaded on the COLLABS project website.

Project brochure

- The brochure will be published at the end of the project. It will contain the project results and will help the network activities after the project conclusion at a local, national and European scale.

Project website and database

- The project website will be developed and maintained by ITML, as one of the main communications and dissemination tools towards the main target audiences, as well as towards the general public. The COLLABS website will allow users to readily collect online information about the project and about issues, which might be of interest to stakeholders. The main objective of the website is to act as the main information platform for the partners, the relevant stakeholders and the general public in order to disseminate as widely as possible the project activities, main events and best practices collected.
- The website will contain deliverables produced as part of the COLLABS project as well as other dissemination and communication items aimed at stakeholders, such as press releases, a project brochure, conference presentations and links to news articles, in which the COLLABS project has been mentioned. In order to assess how well the website is reaching stakeholders and acting as a source of information, the website will use standard web traffic analysis tools to track the number of visitors and similar metrics over the lifetime of the project. The website will be continuously updated throughout the course of the project, and thus will act as a dynamic and up-to-date source of information for stakeholders interested in open access to research data.
- The website will include all relevant information about the project, links, gateway to the data base etc. The deliverables/analysis, databases and any other technical development developed in the framework of COLLABS will be made available on the

website dedicated to the project and will be freely downloadable. It will be designed to present the scope and objectives of COLLABS and will be updated as key milestones are reached.

- The proposed structure of the COLLABS website is the following:
- COLLABS Project - objectives, partners, related projects.
- Deliverables
- Work packages
- Communication - Events; Publications - articles, press-releases; Printed editions - project leaflet, brochure; power point presentation of the project and other means of data as per the requirement of the project.
- Useful information/Links
- Contacts
- The website will be available in English and it will aim at SMEs and their associations. The 'language' spoken will be the one of SMEs. The national versions will be managed by the relevant partners.
- The website can also be a very useful tool for co-operation and internal communication among the partners of the project. The access will be granted by a username and password. The following items could be shared: project draft documents, deliverables, etc. depending on the security standards.

Press releases and articles

At least 12 press releases (one in each quarter) and articles will be prepared in total during the whole project, announcing project objectives, initiatives, events services, and relevant achievements. To ensure transparency of project activities, media may be informed about all project activities and will be invited to all project events, such as conferences, workshops, forum discussion and technical releases.

The aim is to elicit participation and generate interest in COLLABS and related events, draw attention to published reports or drive interested parties to sources such as the project website and make them a useful tool in support of other engagement and dissemination strategies. In addition to English, press releases will be prepared in major European languages for distribution to the media and other stakeholders on completion of specific project milestones and publication of deliverables.

All the project partners will perform this dissemination task. We will also target international press and newsletters in the printed electronics field (such as the OE-A newsletter) and the cold chain field. We will also be publications in social medial such as LinkedIn and Twitter

Social media, including Twitter & blogs

Online social networks are another potentially useful dissemination tool. The COLLABS consortium believes this is a good means of outreach to the public. COLLABS results may be disseminated through popular social networks such as LinkedIn or Twitter. Twitter is a particularly useful way at engaging participants at events and in increasing the impact and

visibility of such events. COLLABS workshops and events will have their own Twitter hashtags. A twitter account has been registered, as:

https://twitter.com/project_collabs

Blogs help to publicize project effort and results and may be particularly effective in reaching particular younger audiences. As part of its media engagement, the consortium will target relevant research blogs to disseminate project knowledge and outcomes. Blogs targeted at particular disciplines, as well as partner blogs, which will be used to promote and facilitate a dialogue around the project activities. The twitter link and live blogs will be added to the project website for easy access and vast publicity. However, the progress and partial results of the project are updated throughout the project duration by all the project partners. All partners will use the company communication channels and forums (conferences, exhibitions, fairs) in which we are active to communicate the results.

Events

Organization and Presentation in Workshops, Seminars & Conferences

Conferences are a means of developing national and international connections with governmental, advocacy or academic opinion leaders, and engaging in a direct, face-to-face communications and discourse. The consortium partners will prepare and deliver papers, slide show presentations and lectures at seminars, relevant events and selected international conferences. A list of conferences to be targeted will be developed throughout the course of the project, with the aim of achieving a good disciplinary and national spread. Consortium partners will participate in key workshops and conferences throughout the course of COLLABS with an open access, in order to increase project visibility and sharing of results, as well as to build the COLLABS contact list as a result of such networking activities.

All partners will identify publication targets and dissemination events, coordinating the joint contributions to such events and the corresponding attendance by the project partners. It will also foster the submission of scientific contributions to reputable conferences and journals and identify potential standardization opportunities. It will additionally strengthen the presence of the project in the most relevant social networks and will also participate in the relevant clustering activities. UniPD will leverage its own dissemination channels (website, LinkedIn, Twitter), as well as presence at industrial exhibitions, panels and workshops. It will use his involvement in IoT Forum and AIOTI to promote the project and to extend the ecosystem.

The COLLABS First year Dissemination related events (i.e., workshop, conferences, summer schools etc) are as follows:

- 1st Workshop on Industrial infrastructures Cyber Security for Advancing Collaborative manufacturing - ICSAC'2021 to be held virtually (Co-located with HiPEAC 2021) January 18th, 2021 - Budapest, H
- Articles in newspapers/website and Blogs
- Researchers Night 2020 Organized by UniPD at Padua Italy
- CPS workshop 2021 at University of Padua promoting COLLABS results.

- International Summer School, 2021 at the University of Padua, Padua, Italy

The COLLABS consortium will also organize various workshops, seminars and conferences as follows.

International events

Various international workshops and conferences are supposed to be organized within the project on the occasion of some international events related to relevant environmental services. Conference and journal publications of high-quality publication venues will be targeted by the project; by disseminating the project results to highly competent researchers apart from creating awareness and influencing the broader research community, useful technical feedback can be received to help steer the project's technical approach in the correct path. A few examples of such targets are (International Conferences) ACM Sensys, ACM Mobisys, USENIX Security, ACMWiSec, IEEE CNS, ACM CCS (International Journals) IEEE Transaction on Mobile Computing, ACM Transactions on Information and System Security, IEEE Transactions on Information Forensics and Security, and IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing.

Initial international workshops

- The main target groups: partners, Enterprise Europe Network EEN members, SMEs and their associations, and local/regional/national stakeholders.
- Aims: initial involvement of other EEN members, synergy with other EEN project, dissemination of initial results, involvement of public bodies, contacts with policy makers / public administrators; sharing the knowledge.
- Main topics: Discussion of interim results of the projects: initial analysis, observatory, beginning of the international network enlargement. Involvement of other public bodies - presentation of best practices. Methodological and technological contributions for the next WPs from other subjects external to the consortium.
- Expected no. of participant: 60 people.

Advanced international workshops

- Main target group: partners, EEN members, SMEs and their associations, local/regional/national stakeholders.
- Aims: involvement of EEN members, synergies with other EEN project, dissemination of results, involvement of SMEs.
- Main topics: Discussion on the preparedness of EEN members to face 1st level services; 2nd level service strategy proposed by COLLABS. Involvement of other public bodies - presentation of best practices.
- Expected no. of participant: 80 people.

International Conferences

Conferences are a means of developing national and international connections with industrial, governmental, advocacy or academic opinion leaders, and engaging in a direct, face-to-face communications and discourse.

- Main target group: EEN members, SMEs associations, SMEs, all stakeholders' categories.
- Aims: public presentation of the project results.
- Main topics: Presentation of the platform, national and international networks, training results, documents for EU policy makers, case studies.

Local workshops

Internally, consortium partners will use workshops to discuss, present and deliberate project related matters and findings. Organization and realization of various local workshops in each Country aimed primarily at local SMEs and local Authorities. There will be dissemination events to be organized in the first 12 months of the project. Further workshops will be organized within WP6 after month 10 and will be dedicated to SMEs and their associations only. Speakers will be the partners, representatives of EEN members with best practices to present, and other relevant groups and individuals.

Due to its previous involvement, UniPD will explore the possibility to host tutorial at summer school. Furthermore, UniPD will address the SME community using IoT meetup. In order to lower the entry barriers, UNSPMF and HUA will contribute to internal experts' workshops and tutorials and will distribute training material to developers. All consortium partners will leverage their role of co-organizer and sponsor of the Web of Things workshop. Moreover, UNIPD and all partners will contribute to information dissemination through conference participation and by organizing talks in different universities around Europe. In addition, the possibility of organizing workshops on the topic will be investigated.

- Expected no. of participant: At least 20 people per workshop.

The consortium will also convene a final high-level event for the project. This event will provide the opportunity for different categories of stakeholder to engage with the consortium partners and discuss the project's research, methodologies and findings. The event seeks to stimulate an exchange of the project's conclusions and recommendations with stakeholders and promote interaction among different types of stakeholders, including policymakers, MEPs, representatives from the Member States and local authority representatives, as well as civil protection authorities, academia and industry. The high-level event will constitute the final conference/meeting of the project.

- Outcome measure: number of conference papers, number of conference workshops, type and size of conference, conference attendance.

The mapping of various dissemination tools explained in Sections 3 and 4 in this document that the consortium will use to target specific stakeholder categories are arranged in Table 1.

Table 1: Mapping of dissemination tools to stakeholder groups

Stakeholders	Dissemination Tools
<u>Government</u> International Organizations European Commission	E-mails Project website Focus groups, workshops, reflection group

<p><i>Policy makers and MEPs/MPs at European and Member State level</i> <i>Regulatory, administrative or public authorities including planners, operators and users of security systems (e.g. local authorities, law enforcement authorities, etc.)</i></p>	<p><i>High-level final event</i> <i>Conferences</i> <i>Press releases</i> <i>Media communications</i></p>
<p><u>Industry</u> <i>Manufacturers</i> <i>Suppliers</i> <i>Service providers</i> <i>Vendors</i> <i>System integrators</i> <i>Industry associations (including trade and labour organisations)</i></p>	<p><i>Project website</i> <i>Press releases</i> <i>Conferences</i> <i>Media communications</i> <i>Workshops (reflection group)</i> <i>Journal Publications</i></p>
<p><u>Critical infrastructure operators</u></p>	<p><i>Project website</i> <i>E-mail</i> <i>Press releases</i> <i>Conferences</i> <i>Media communications</i></p>
<p><u>Civil protection authorities and first responders</u></p>	<p><i>Project website</i> <i>E-mail</i> <i>Press releases</i> <i>Conferences</i> <i>Media communications</i> <i>Workshops (reflection group)</i></p>
<p><u>Media</u> <i>Blogs</i> <i>Journals</i> <i>Newspapers</i> <i>Radio</i> <i>Television</i> <i>Websites</i></p>	<p><i>Project</i> <i>Website</i> <i>Press releases</i> <i>Media communications Features</i> <i>E-mails</i> <i>Telephone</i></p>
<p><u>Academia, research institutions and think tanks</u></p>	<p><i>Journal articles</i> <i>E-mail</i> <i>Project website</i> <i>Conferences</i></p>
<p><u>Civil society organizations and the public</u></p>	<p><i>E-mail</i> <i>Press releases</i> <i>Media communications</i> <i>Project website</i> <i>Workshops (reflection group)</i> <i>Social networks</i></p>

Table 2 demonstrates that different communication strategies that are best suited to different target groups at various levels of dissemination. Therefore, as project deliverables become available or as events or research exercises are undertaken, the consortium will consider which Target/stakeholder groups the deliverable (or event or research exercise) is most applicable to

and will publicize the activity using those means of communications. Towards the end of the project, we will pay particular attention to preparing guidelines for different target groups and disseminate them accordingly. In the final report on dissemination, due at the end of the project, we will reflect on the success of our dissemination activities by looking at the outcome measures for each of the tools. For events organized by COLLABS we will conduct evaluations after the event by sending questionnaires to participants.

Table 2: Timetable of communication strategies

<i>Dissemination level</i>	<i>Means of Communication</i>	<i>Target groups</i>
<i>Local level</i>	<i>Pamphlet Brochure Internet website Press releases Articles Local workshops Company visits</i>	<i>SMEs; Trade and Professional associations presented at local level; Municipalities and regional administrations</i>
<i>National level</i>	<i>Pamphlet Brochure Internet website Press releases Articles Local workshops</i>	<i>SMEs; Trade and Professional associations ; National public authorities; National EEN consortiums ;</i>
<i>European level</i>	<i>Pamphlet; Brochure ; website ; Press releases ; Articles ; International conferences of the project; Conferences, trainings, sector group meetings and website of EEN; Cooperation agreement;</i>	<i>Member of Enterprise Europe Network</i>

Dissemination and Communication Events by Each Partner

Dissemination and communication plan by each partner

Below each partner individually elaborates their dissemination strategies for the Y1 and Y2, Y3 in the light of above-mentioned description.

Commissariat A L Energie Atomique Et Aux Energies Alternatives (CEA)

- Y1 Dissemination and communication strategies:**

The project has been disseminated internally to CEA LIST DILS (Software and Hardware Systems Integration) together with other projects in the manufacturing domain. A public press release is in preparation and will be transmitted on CEA and COLLABS Twitter channels together with UniPD.

Externally, COLLABS has been presented by CEA at Made in Europe Webinar on 17th September 2020 together with several other projects on manufacturing.

- **Y2/Y3 Dissemination and communication strategies:**

CEA will continue disseminating the project's result to all possible scientific events as well as European events and establish links with other R&D projects from the same area. This includes international events as well as events organized by the EC, CEA and its partners.

For any possible event, CEA will propose participation to the project partners and discuss with the Technical Leader the interest of any such opportunity.

Foundation for Research & Technology Hellas (FORTH)

- **Y1 Dissemination and communication strategies:**

FORTH has participated in one conference and one workshop where it published research results related to the work carried out within COLLABS. Due to health safety restrictions these events were organized in the form of virtual conferences and FORTH participated in their online activities (online presentations, virtual meeting rooms and teleconference sessions).

The two papers published were the following:

1. D. Deyannis, D. Karnikis, G. Vasiliadis, S. Ioannidis, "An Enclave Assisted Snapshot-based Kernel Integrity Monitor," in 3rd International Workshop on Edge Systems, Analytics and Networking (EdgeSys), April 2020.
2. N. Chalkiadakis, D. Deyannis, D. Karnikis, G. Vasiliadis, S. Ioannidis, "The Million Dollar Handshake Secure and Attested Communications in the Cloud," in IEEE International Conference on Cloud Computing 2020 (IEEE CLOUD 2020), October 2020.

In addition to conferences and workshops, FORTH has also published a paper in the ACM Transactions on Architecture and Code Optimization (TACO) journal:

- G. Christou, G. Vasiliadis, V. Papaefsthathiou, A. Papadogiannakis, S. Ioannidis, "On Architectural Support for Instruction Set Randomization," ACM Transactions on Architecture and Code Optimization (TACO) 17, 4, Article 36 (November 2020).

- **Y2/Y3 Dissemination and communication strategies:**

FORTH plans to continue disseminating COLLABS work in scientific events such as workshops and conferences and will suggest shared activities and events with other Horizon projects to promote the dissemination of the project.

PHILIPS Consumer Lifestyle B.V. (PCL)

- **Y1 Dissemination and communication strategies:**

LinkedIn:

All PCL project members post the following line on their LinkedIn profile:

"Involved in the Horizon 2020 EU COLLABS (COverprehensive cyber-intelligence framework for resilient coLLABorative manufacturing Systems) project - <https://www.collabs-project.eu>"

All PCL project members follow the LinkedIn Collabs Project to further increase visibility.

When posts are made through this account PCL members will share these posts to their LinkedIn network on a regular basis. This reaches the strategic focus areas of Local, National, European and dissemination outside of the European level over a largely-varied audience.

Informal communications:

All PCL project members commit to disseminating knowledge about the COLLABS project to their informal industrial 4.0 network whenever it is deemed applicable. Key communication messages, as defined by the consortium, will be used to disseminate news. These activities shall take place using face to face meetings (limited due to COVID-19) and online conferencing. Philips participates in Local (Innovation Cluster Drachten, Smart Industry Hub) and National (AI coalition) initiatives such as a digital innovation hubs which will also be used as a place to disseminate knowledge about the COLLABS project.

Participation:

As a use case demonstrator and not a technology provider PCL will participate where possible in presentations, workshops and events when requested to do so by technology providers. The intent will most likely be to share experiences and background in manufacturing and industry 4.0 as it relates to COLLABS.

- **Y2/Y3 Dissemination and communication strategies:**

LinkedIn:

All PCL project members post the following line on their LinkedIn profile:

"Involved in the Horizon 2020 EU COLLABS (COMprehensive cyber-intelligence framework for resilient coLLABorative manufacturing Systems) project - <https://www.collabs-project.eu>"

All PCL project members follow the LinkedIn Collabs Project to further increase visibility.

When posts are made through this account PCL members will share these posts to their LinkedIn network on a regular basis. This reaches the strategic focus areas of Local, National, European and dissemination outside of the European level over a large varied audience.

Informal communications:

All PCL project members commit to disseminating knowledge about the COLLABS project to their informal industrial 4.0 network whenever it is deemed applicable. Key communication messages as defined by the consortium will be used to disseminate news. These activities shall take place using face to face meetings (limited due to COVID-19) and online conferencing. Philips participates in Local (Innovation Cluster Drachten, Smart Industry Hub) and National (AI coalition) initiatives such as a digital innovation hubs which will also be used as a place to disseminate knowledge about the COLLABS project.

Participation:

As a use case demonstrator and not a technology provider PCL will participate where possible in presentations, workshops and events when requested to do so by technology providers. The intent will most likely be to share experiences and background in manufacturing and industry 4.0 as it relates to COLLABS.

Infineon Technologies AG (IFAG)

- **Y1 Dissemination and communication strategies:**

LinkedIn:

All the IFAG project members follow the account of COLLABS in LinkedIn and share their publications.

Events:

IFAG organized the event “Infineon’s virtual show 2020” to exchange the newest innovations and trends. It took place the 10-13 November 2020. In this event decentralized applications were references, were COLLABS is an important trend in industry.

- **Y2/Y3 Dissemination and communication strategies:**

LinkedIn:

All the IFAG project members follow the account of COLLABS in LinkedIn and share their publications.

Events: In different events organized or attended by IFAG related with decentralized security, IFAG will disseminate the COLLABS news.

Publications: IFAG is currently working in several publications related with the work realized in COLLABS. These papers will be published the next year and COLLABS will be referenced.

ADVANCED LABORATORY ON EMBEDDED SYSTEMS SRL (UTRC)

- **Y1 Dissemination and communication strategies:**

LinkedIn:

All ALES project members follow the LinkedIn COLLABS Project to further increase visibility and commit to share this account posts to their network, in order to reach a broad audience of professionals in industry and academia.

Participation:

In the first year ALES participates at the following events presenting COLLABS in general and providing the audience with a peak of its early results:

- We have presented at the International Online Winter School on Blockchain Technology and Applications Hyperledger, where we present our design of a blockchain-based supply chain management created in the COLLABS context
 - We have presented the COLLABS project at SeCollA - Secure Collaborative Intelligent Industrial Assets workshop
- ALES plans also to participate when possible in other conferences and workshop to further share the COLLABS project results and get feedbacks from the community.

Organization:

In the first year, ALES, in collaboration with SAG and UNSPMF, organized the ICSAC workshop - 1st Workshop on Industrial infrastructures Cyber Security for Advancing Collaborative manufacturing. This workshop is co-located with HiPEAC and hosts presentations from the main technological work packages in COLLABS.

- **Y2/Y3 Dissemination and communication strategies:**

LinkedIn:

All ALES project members follow the LinkedIn COLLABS Project to further increase visibility and commit to share this accounts posts to their network, in order to reach a broad audience of professionals in industry and academia.

Participation:

In the next years, ALES plans to submit papers (currently under draft) and participate as speakers to scientific conferences in the field of industrial cyber security. ALES plans also to participate when possible in other conferences and workshop to further share the COLLABS project results and get feedbacks from the community.

Organization:

In the next years, ALES, if the first edition is a success, plans to organize more editions of ICSAC workshop. We also envision our possible help other events organized by other consortium members.

University of Novi Sad Faculty of Sciences (UNSPMF):

UNSPMF's communication and dissemination strategy, related to the COLLABS project, will be evolved, in order to align with the project progress and newly available opportunities. The Communication and Dissemination plan is based on a responsive framework that adapts to the needs and challenges. The plan will follow a communication strategy that formulates key messages tailored to the needs and expectations of the various target audiences (citizens, academia, industry and government). UNSPMF will be committed to exploiting and rationalizing the networks and dissemination and communication channels that are already in existence at partner institutions and related projects that can reach the specific stakeholder of interest.

- **Y1 Dissemination and communication strategies:**

LinkedIn:

All UNSPMF project members follow the LinkedIn COLLABS Project profile in order to support visibility of the future COLLABS achievements among the citizens, academia, industry and government.

Participation:

UNSPMF participates at the following events presenting COLLABS in general and its early results:

- SeCoIIA - Secure Collaborative Intelligent Industrial Assets workshop

ALES plans also to participate when is possible in other conferences and workshop to further share the COLLABS project results and get feedbacks from the community.

Organization:

Together ALES and SAG, UNSPMF organized a workshop dedicated to the main technical challenges in COLLABS named 1st Workshop on Industrial infrastructures Cyber Security for Advancing Collaborative manufacturing. This ICSAC workshop has been co-located with HiPEAC.

- **Y2/Y3 Dissemination and communication strategies:**

LinkedIn:

UNSPMF will use COLLABS LinkedIn account for communication with stakeholders and dissemination of project activities. UNSPMF will provide updates on the project activities, and its results, events and photos or other material that we think is useful and can inform and engage our audience.

Participation:

UNSPMF plans to participate on the events, publish articles and papers, collaborate with other projects, and participate in the relevant exhibitions in order to present share the COLLABS project results and to get feedbacks from the community.

Organization:

The main technical outcomes, activities and results will be disseminated in the various workshops with the main aim objective to inform, collect and summarize the learnings for future exploitation. Also, the UNSPMF team will use its University courses to present project results with aim to share knowledge and to support establishing of a community of future industrial engineers around COLLABS solution.

Sphynx Technology Solutions AG (STS)

- **Y1 Dissemination and communication strategies:**

LinkedIn and Twitter:

All STS members involved in COLLABS follow the LinkedIn and Twitter COLLABS Project to further increase visibility and commit to share this account's posts to their network, in order to reach a broad audience of professionals in industry and academia.

Organization and Presentation:

In the first year STS was a sponsor of the 3rd International Conference on Cybersecurity 4 Maritime, Oil & Gas, Energy (CypBER 2020). The event was to be held in Nicosia, Cyprus, on the 10th of March 2020, but due to the COVID-19 situation, the event was finally held online on the 3rd of June 2020. The scope of CypBER 2020 was of significant relevance to the Industrial IoT applications covered within COLLABS, as it focused on pertinent industries (Maritime, Oil & Gas and Energy) with presentations touching topics such as the cybersecurity protection of critical infrastructures at the EU-level, the cybersecurity of ports and sea transport, Upstream-Midstream-Downstream Oil & Gas industry, and traditional and renewable energy infrastructures. STS, as a sponsor, had a slot in the main program of the conference, where the company had the opportunity to present its Model-driven Cyber Security Risk Management approach, which is also at the heart of the Security Assurance Tool integrated into COLLABS. In fact, the application of said approach in the context of COLLABS was one of the use cases presented by STS during the conference. The participants also had the chance to be informed about the COLLABS project and its proposed approach at the virtual booth that STS had in place, where all company R&D activities were presented.

- **Y2/Y3 Dissemination and communication strategies:**

LinkedIn and Twitter:

All STS project members will keep following the LinkedIn and Twitter COLLABS Project to further increase visibility and commit to share this accounts posts to their network in order to reach a broad audience of professionals in industry and academia.

Participation:

In the next years, STS plans to submit papers and present COLLABS' results into relevant conferences and workshops. STS plans also to participate, even without necessarily presenting a paper, when possible, in certain large audience European conferences and workshops (like for example HiPEAC and DATE) to further, informally, share the COLLABS project results and get feedback from the community.

THALES SIX GTS FR SAS (TSG)

- **Y1 Dissemination and communication strategies:**

LinkedIn:

All TSG project members follow the LinkedIn Collabs Project to further increase visibility. Our aim is to share posts on a regular basis. This will increase the visibility over a largely-varied audience at the national, and European level.

Participation:

TSG will participate in presentations, workshops, and events. The aim is to share our background in security and industry 4.0, as it relates to COLLABS, and to disseminate project

results as TSG is WP3 leader. TSG also plans to submit papers in cyber security conferences and journals.

- **Y2/Y3 Dissemination and communication strategies:**

LinkedIn:

All TSG project members will commit to increase visibility in order to reach a broad audience from industry and academia.

Participation:

In the next years TSG plans to submit more technical papers in the field of security in industry 4.0. TSG plans also to participate in conference and workshops in order to share the COLLABS project technical achievements.

Information Technology for Market Leadership IKE (ITML):

- **Y1 Dissemination and communication strategies:**

ITML is responsible for the content of the website - <https://www.collabs-project.eu> , using the input provided from all partners to populate the website's blog accordingly. ITML was responsible for the creation of a video dedicated for informing the public of COLLABS' overall objectives.

We have circulated COLLABS LinkedIn account amongst ITML's staff, especially ones who are members of the project, to increase its visibility. We are also using our LinkedIn, Twitter, and Facebook channels to post and share any information related to the project, which includes sharing the regular posts from COLLABS' LinkedIn & Twitter accounts.

ITML members involved in COLLABS shall attend and/or participate in events such as workshops and conferences to further publicize the project amongst prospected stakeholders and entities concerned, along with disseminating the project in informal meetings with entities mentioned above.

- **Y2/Y3 Dissemination and communication strategies:**

ITML is responsible for the content of the website - <https://www.collabs-project.eu> , using the input provided from all partners to populate the website's blog accordingly. Consequently, we will be supporting UniPD with the creation of any means of communication which includes brochures, pamphlets, and other visual dissemination tools such as more videos or COLLABS framework demos.

We will also be using our LinkedIn, Twitter, and Facebook channels to post and share any information related to the project, which includes sharing the regular posts from COLLABS' LinkedIn & Twitter accounts.

ITML members involved in COLLABS shall attend and/or participate in events such as workshops and conferences to further publicize the project amongst prospected stakeholders and entities concerned, along with disseminating the project in informal meetings with entities mentioned above.

University of Padova (UNIPD)

- **Y1 Dissemination and communication strategies:**

Social networking platform: UniPD have circulated the COLLABS LinkedIn account amongst UniPD faculty and members of the project. We are also using the platforms of our LinkedIn, Twitter, and Facebook medium to post and share any information related to the project to increase the visibility of the project happenings and events.

Events: UniPD members involved in the COLLABS project are motivated to engage themselves in workshops and conferences to utilize the technical networking for upholding the project purposes among the suitable stakeholders.

- **Y2/Y3 Dissemination and communication strategies:**

Events: For Y2/Y3, UniPD plans to have one workshop on cyber-physical systems for engaging different stakeholders to obtain a clear visibility of the scope of the COLLABS project.

Publications: UniPD objectifies the dissemination strategy by publishing the research outputs in scientific journals and conference proceedings for the visibility among scientific community and exploring the future collaborations. For Y2/Y3, UniPD plans to have at least 2 journal papers and 1 conference paper communication and probable publication.

SIEMENS AG (SAG)

- **Y1 Dissemination and communication strategies:**

LinkedIn:

The project members of SAG are following the profile of the COLLABS project on LinkedIn and are committed to share and further distribute posts via their networks in order to promote the project and increase its visibility amongst colleagues and connected partners.

Internal Dissemination and Communication:

SAG is one of the partners of COLLABS that is also engaged in EFFRA¹ (the European Factories of the Future Research Association). The project members engaged in COLLABS have had multiple meetings with colleagues working on EFFRA, thus, making sure that both projects are

¹ <https://www.effra.eu/>

well connected, provide input in both directions, and can benefit from synergies. Furthermore, the project members of SAG are part of SAG's Technology department and work closely with the R&D teams in SAG's divisions. In the first year, this linkage was used to promote the technology roadmap to partners in the divisions.

Organization:

SAG contributed together with ALES and UNSPMF to the planning and organization of the first ICSAC workshop² that will take place in January via virtual meetings cause of COVID-19 restrictions. ICSAC is collocated with HiPEAC 2021³.

- **Y2/Y3 Dissemination and communication strategies:**

LinkedIn:

The project members of SAG will continue to follow and promote the COLLABS project on LinkedIn to increase its visibility.

Internal Dissemination and Communication:

SAG will continue the successful exchange between COLLABS and EFFRA also in the second and third year of the project, aiming at disseminations in both directions. That is, for instance, inviting representatives of EFFRA to COLLABS' events. Also, the interaction with SAG's divisions to promote COLLABS' results in R&D projects will be continued.

Publications:

SAG is currently working on a joint publication together with ALES for presenting the work developed in T2.6 on managing access control in the context of remote maintenance use cases. Apart from this already planned publication, SAG aims to publish further results from the successful cooperation in the project over the next two years at appropriate conferences.

RENAULT SAS (REN)

- **Y1 Dissemination and communication strategies:**

LinkedIn:

All REN project members follow the LinkedIn Collabs Project and share posts to their network to further increase visibility.

This reaches the strategic focus areas of Local, National, European and dissemination outside of the European level over a varied audience. Some of the REN project members are also involved inside the Renault-Nissan-Mitsubishi Alliance which provide a large international network which covers many industries and research organizations.

² <https://www.collabs-project.eu/icsac-2021-workshop/>

³ <https://www.hipeac.net/2021/spring-virtual/#/>

Informal communications:

ALL REN project members are also involved in the departments that define the cybersecurity strategy for the manufacturing environment: OT cybersecurity department, IS/IT cybersecurity department and Industry 4.0 / connected plant team.

For the first year, and this will continue all long the project, COLLABS will feed the REN manufacturing cybersecurity strategy. Project members will disseminate knowledge about the COLLABS project and identify any opportunity where results will be applicable.

Project members has participated on the first year to various REN webinars related to Industry 4.0 innovations. COLLABS project has been presented to a large audience, at the international level, covering all the Renault-Nissan partners inside the Alliance (Renault, Nissan, Mitsubishi).

Participation:

As a use case demonstrator and not a technology provider, REN will participate where possible in presentations, workshops and events when requested to do so by technology providers. The intent will most likely be to share experiences and background in manufacturing and industry 4.0, as it relates to COLLABS.

- **Y2/Y3 Dissemination and communication strategies:**

Social Media:

All REN project members will continue their contribution, started during the first year, to increase the visibility of all the events, news and posts shared over LinkedIn.

REN project members has also started discussions with the corporate communication department, to organize on Y2/Y3 a recurrent communication about the COLLABS project on all the official Renault social media communication channels. This should reach the strategic focus areas of Local, National, European and dissemination outside of the European level over a large varied audience, since Renault Group has millions of followers over the world.

Informal communications:

All REN project members will continue their dissemination activities inside the group, sharing knowledge and opportunities about COLLABS project. Project uses all internal communication tools (internal social media), to inform about the COLLABS project, and members will continue to organize communications activities internally, meetings, to present COLLABS innovations and opportunities. Communication activities will be focused on Industry 4.0 teams in manufacturing and supply-chain departments.

Events:

As a use case demonstrator and not a technology provider REN will participate where possible in presentations, workshops and events, when requested, to do so by technology providers. The intent will most likely be to share experiences and background in manufacturing and industry 4.0 as it relates to COLLABS.

REN project members have also contacted internal public funding and R&D departments, to identify national or international events to participate and present the COLLABS project.

HAROKOPIO UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS (HUA)

- **Y1 Dissemination and communication strategies:**

For the first year of the project, HUA made sure to communicate the project and disseminate its results; mainly through digital channels, namely its website, linkedIn accounts and the personal web pages of the involved team members. Furthermore, it made sure to provide the project overview in any given chance, such as in meetings of other research projects. Furthermore, the faculty members involved in the project, communicated the project intended outcomes to the students of their respective classes.

- **Y2/Y3 Dissemination and communication strategies:**

The tip of the edge of the dissemination strategy of HUA is to publish the results of our work in scientific journals and conference proceedings and subsequently present those results in the conferences audience. For Y2/Y3, we plan to have at least 2 journal and 3 conference papers submitted.

Dissemination and Communication Plan

The dissemination activities of the project are based upon a delivery schedule. The scheduling of these activities is closely aligned with key project deliverables. There are three deliverables associated with the 1st year dissemination strategy of COLLABS (lead partner indicated in brackets):

- Deliverable 7.3 - Proposal for Dissemination strategy, due at the end of Month 3, to be reviewed in Months 10 & 17 (UniPD).
- Deliverable 7.3 - Website, due at end of Month 3, but already up and running from kick-off meeting (ITML).
- Deliverable 7.3 - Report on dissemination activities, due at end of Month 12 (UniPD).

Conclusion

This dissemination strategy provides the COLLABS project with a solid framework with which to begin disseminating project deliverables and activities. The COLLABS consortium will use this as an initial strategy which will be further reviewed, revised and updated as dissemination materials and specific strategies are evaluated for their reach, effectiveness in targeting particular end users, stakeholders and alignment with stakeholder interests and barriers. This document, and more importantly the dissemination strategy will act as a live document; will be revisited in months 12 and 24 in light of increasing experience. COLLABS poses particular challenges for effective dissemination, given the variety of stakeholders involved. However, we have already made good progress in identifying stakeholders, and their own challenges. Consortium members have a wide range of experiences in all of the different dissemination tools that we have identified and included in this report.